

The Impact of Ownership Structure and Dividend Pay-out on Financial Performance: Evidence from GCC Banking Sector

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Abstract

This paper examined the impact of Ownership Structure and Dividend pay-out on bank financial performance for the top 10 listed banks in GCC countries from 2009 to 2020 (Post CRISIS). This study applies the ordinary least square (OLS) technique to estimate the panel data regression. The findings suggest a positive and significant impact of ownership structure on the performance of banks. It also shows that the association between dividend payout and bank performance is positive. The findings indicate that market participants' awareness about the value of strong ownership structure measures has grown over time. This leads to greater adoption of those measures by shareholders which indeed influences a bank's performance.

Keywords: Ownership Structure, Dividend Pay-out, Financial Performance, Banks, GCC.

1. Introduction

The ownership structure is a pledge by shareholders to cede control to managers at various levels. The ownership structure of a bank is one of the most important factors impacting its corporate governance (Amran & Ahmad, 2011). It is one of the most important corporate governance measures that has attracted the attention of several scholars in recent years (Adebiyi, & Olowookere, 2013; and Kumar & Zattoni, 2013). It is considered a critical aspect that affects the health of a bank (Zeitun & Tian, 2007). It is assumed that a bank's ownership structure is of major importance as they affect the decision-making process and thereby the economic efficiency of the bank being managed. The existence and expansion of a business are both

dependent on the level of ownership. It is anticipated that a bank's performance is influenced by its ownership structure (Imoleayo, Eddy, & Oluku, 2020). Since shareholders determine management incentives and, as a result, the economic productivity of the companies they control, the ownership structure is a significant corporate governance instrument (Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

Dividend payout is one of the most essential aspects of banking regulations, and it has been a topic of discussion in the literature. The value of a bank is affected by dividend payout decisions. Furthermore, cash dividends have a unique status among shareholders. The key issue, though, is why a policy of dividend payout was adopted in the first place. Various factors influence dividend policy. Corporate governance is one of these factors. Due to recent financial scandals, corporate governance has attracted great attention. The motivation for the focus is the conflict of interest among shareholders in the bank structure (Gillan and Starks, 2003). There are differences in the types of shareholders and the demand for dividends (Truong and Heaney, 2007). The author argues that Institutional shareholders and managerial shareholders have a higher influence on bank policy than other types of shareholders.

The existing literature indicated the link between a bank's dividend policy, ownership structure, and bank performance (Short et al., 2002). Different countries have different dividend strategies (Laporta et al., 2000). According to previous research, there are considerable disparities in dividend payout between developed and developing countries (Abdelsalam et al., 2008). Previous studies including (Claessens et al., 2000) claimed that environmental factors influence bank governance practices, including ownership structure. As a result, in different situations and nations, the association between ownership structure, dividend policies, and performance is expected to be different.

2. Literature Review

Numerous studies have been done to investigate the nature of ownership structure. Furthermore, (Briano-Turrent et al., 2016; Brown & Caylor, 2009) discovered that the ownership score has a positive and statistically significant effect on financial performance. Likewise, Garca-Meca and Sánchez-Ballesta (2011) investigate the implications on Tobin's Q of three aspects of

the Spanish ownership structure that are expected to reflect competing interests: ownership concentration, insider ownership, and bank ownership in the Spanish market. According to the research, concentrated ownership has a significant positive influence on firm performance up to a particular level, but once that level is exceeded, the effect becomes negative. Insider and institutional ownership, on the other hand, have a negligible impact on firm performance.

Furthermore, [Nguyen et al. \(2015\)](#) validate the commonly held position of agency theory concerning the effective monitoring impact of significant shareholders in Singapore and Vietnam. They discover indications that ownership concentration has a positive impact on performance. They also discover that the quality of national governance matters when it comes to describing the influence of concentrated ownership on bank performance. [Almudehki and Zeitun \(2013\)](#), on the other hand, investigate the impact of various ownership dimensions (board ownership, foreign ownership, institutional ownership, and ownership concentration) on the performance of 29 firms listed on the Doha Stock Exchange between 2006 and 2011. They discover that board, foreign, and concentrated ownership all affect firm performance.

Similarly, [Zeitun \(2014\)](#) examines the entire GCC market and discovers that ownership structure, ownership concentration, and government ownership all have a beneficial impact on bank performance in these economies. However, he discovers that institutional and foreign ownership have little effect on these banks' performance. [Arouri et al. \(2014\)](#) report varying outcomes for 58 banks operating in GCC markets. They discover that family, foreign, and institutional ownership have a beneficial impact on bank performance, but that government ownership does not affect performance. Furthermore, the preceding arguments show that different levels of concentrated ownership (5 percent, 10%, 20%, and 25%) may have distinct consequences on company performance.

Many research' results reveal that dividend payments have a considerable impact on financial performance ([Musiega et al., 2013](#); [Boamah, et al., 2014](#); [Alzomaia, & Al-Khadhiri, 2013](#); [Okpara & Chigozie, 2010](#); [Mehta, 2012](#)). [Musiega et al. \(2013\)](#) used purposive sampling to evaluate factors influencing dividend distribution policy for Nairobi Securities Exchange financial firms from 2007 to 2011. The researchers investigated the relationship between dividend payout and other parameters using descriptive statistics and multiple regressions.

Furthermore, [Ling et al. \(2008\)](#) investigated the profitability as a function of dividend payout ratio in Malaysia, using a sample of 100 institutions listed on the Bursa Malaysia. As parameters, they employed return on assets and return on equity. They also demonstrate that ROE and ROA have high correlations with dividend payment ratios. Another study, undertaken by [Boamah et al. \(2014\)](#), examined the industry sector determinants of dividend policy and their impact on stock values of banks listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange (GSE) from 2006 to 2011. Their results demonstrated that Profit After-Tax is a crucial variable evaluated by most sectors when paying dividends, implying that Profitability is a key predictor of the dividend policy of companies across the GSE.

According to [Amidu and Abor \(2006\)](#), there is a considerable negative link between profitability and dividend payout. As a result, corporations choose to retain their gains rather than give them out as dividends. These findings are reinforced by [Okpara and Chigozie \(2010\)](#), who discovered that when a firm's incomes rise, dividends decrease, implying that firms invest their surplus revenues in expansion rather than issuing dividends. [Mehta \(2012\)](#), on the other hand, investigated UAE banks from 2005 to 2009 and determined that bank profitability as measured by ROE has a negative connection with dividend payout, implying that the most profitable banks pay lower dividends.

Current earnings, on the other hand, were found to be positively connected with dividend payout. According to the results of a study conducted by [Alzomaia and Al-Khadhiri \(2013\)](#) on Saudi Arabian stock exchanges, earnings per share were substantial and had a positive association with dividends per share, implying that when bank raise their profitability, payouts per share increase. [Mohammed and Mohammed \(2012\)](#) discovered that profitability, as measured by earnings per share (EPS), has the greatest and most significant impact on dividends in their research on a worthy factor influencing dividend policy decisions, an empirical study on industrial corporations listed on an Amman stock exchange.

Shifting to another variable, [Fu et al. \(2014\)](#) indicated a positive relationship between the bank's SIZE and Tobin's Q and a negative relationship with the bank's first year lag of bank assets. It suggests that stakeholders might concentrate on synergistically enhanced asset volume in the short term, but this might have an adverse impact on the value of the investors in the long

term. According to [Fiordelisi and Molyneux \(2010\)](#), there is a positive and significant relationship between the size of the assets and the value of the shareholders. Bigger banks face a rise in SIZE, slightly reducing costs and inefficiencies in the scale. [Micco, Panizza, and Yanez \(2007\)](#) found that the profitability of the bank (ROA) and SIZE had an insignificant positive association.

[Mamatzakis & Bermpei \(2017\)](#) conclude that LR and bank profitability measured by ROA, NIM, and ROE has a significantly positive association. Moreover, [Srairi \(2009\)](#) found that the profitability of a traditional bank has a significantly positive association with the LR ratio, which suggests a negative relationship between the amount of the bank's liquid assets and the bank's profitability. Furthermore, [Tran, Lin, and Nguyen \(2016\)](#) claim that liquidity risk and bank profitability are adversely associated, indicating that reduced liquidity is responsible for greater profitability and risks. However, [Ongore and Kusa \(2013\)](#) do not find a statistical relationship between bank performance measured by NIM, ROA, and ROE and LR ratios. It implies that bank profitability is not dependent on the amount of liquid assets.

The LLPs ratio indicates variation in interim regulations and is a direct measure for the variation in creditworthiness in all nations. Variations in the LLPs ratio may reflect the intensity of the financial institution loan portfolio that may affect bank quality. The variance in LLPs could lead to a loan performance dispute. [Djalilov and Piesse \(2016\)](#) conclude a negative relationship between LLPs and bank performance as measured by ROA, ROE, and Tobin's Q. [Vong & Chan \(2009\)](#) emphasized that due to some reasons, banks' risk-averse approach leads to declined profitability. Firstly, based on accounting standards, banks' annual income is supplied to LLPs; secondly, banks reach the highest profits once they engage in more loan practices, when bank provision levels are high, their capacity to give loans will decrease, thereby significantly depressing the bank's ROA.

Generally, the low quality of the assets restricts the range of loanable capital of the bank; its profitability could also be reduced. Although the evidence of this argument has frequently been established in developed nations, it is not common in emerging and developing nations. [Osugwa \(2014\)](#), found a negative relationship between NPLs and bank profitability as measured by Tobin's Q. [Mamatzakis & Bermpei \(2017\)](#) and [Ongore & Kusa \(2013\)](#) note that the value of the

portfolio of loans has a significant impact on the performance of commercial banks. Their results indicate that bank performance as measured by ROA, ROE, NIM is significantly and negatively linked with the NPLs ratio. The interpretation of their result is that weak bank performance is either due to inadequate asset quality or heavy NPLs. This is because loans comprise the most significant share of earnings assets in the bank balance sheet.

Table:1
Summary of Related Literature

Author/ Year	Country	Period	Methodology	Empirical Result
<i>Arouri et al. / 2014</i>	GCC Countries	2010-2011	Multivariate Regression Analysis	Family ownership, foreign ownership, and institutional ownership has a significant positive association with bank performance
<i>Rami Zeitun / 2014</i>	GCC Countries	2000-2010	2SLS and OLS	Ownership concentration affects firm performance positively and significantly
<i>Noora Almudehki /2011</i>	Qatar	2006-2011	Fixed and random effect	A positive relationship between ownership structure and financial performance
<i>Tuan et al, / 2015</i>	Singapore& Vietnam	2008-2011	Two Step GMM	A positive effect of ownership structure on performance
<i>Emma & Juan/ 2011</i>	Spain	1999-2002	OLS	A positive link between ownership structure and bank performance
<i>Lawrence et al., /2008</i>	USA	2003-2008	OLS	The negative impact of ownership structure on bank performance
<i>Ayse & Bradley/ 2020</i>	USA	1992-14	Fixed effect and VAR	Bank size has a positive relation with cost efficiency and returns to scale
<i>Titko/ 2016</i>	European Union	2008-14	OLS	Bank profitability and SIZE have an insignificant relationship
<i>Chen et al., /2016</i>	USA	2002-12	2SLS, Heckman, and OLS	Bank risk and increased liquidity have a negative relationship
<i>Djebali & Zaghdoudi /2020</i>	MENA	1999-17	Fixed Effect and PSTR Model	There is a positive relationship between liquidity risk and bank stability
<i>Simper et al., / 2019</i>	Europe	2002-14	GMM	The result shows that LLPs in Euro banks increase due

<i>Meles et al. /2016</i>	USA	2005-12	OLS	to bad management practices Bank profitability (ROE, ROA) is positively significant and insignificant lined to LLPs
<i>Abdelaziz et al., / 2020</i>	MENA	2004-15	OLS	A negative relationship between bank credit risk NPLs and bank profitability ROA
<i>Fah and Nasir / 2014</i>	4 Asia Pacific Countries	2000-08	OLS	A negative relationship between NPLs and bank profitability.

3. Methodology

3.1 Sample Selection

This study is quantitative in nature uses a correlational research design to look into the direct impact of ownership structures and dividend payouts on the financial performance of listed banks in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries. During the assessment, the predicted relationship between the variables was the main focus. This is because a statistical link between parameters may not be of much benefit because it is likely to lead to biased results. This study is based on secondary data covering the period of 11 years i.e. from 2009 to 2011. The year 2009 was chosen because of the financial crisis in 2008, which had a significant influence on the GCC banking sector. The data for this study derives from the published annual reports of the listed banks. These data were obtained manually from the banks' published annual reports as well as the websites of the chosen banks.

3.2 Variables Description

In order to examine the financial performance of listed banks on GCC stock exchanges, following Trad et al. (2017); Liang et al. (2013); and Pan and Tian (2014), this study include ROA (Return on Assets), ROE (Return on Equity), and Tobin's Q as dependent variables. Return on Assets (ROA) is a metric that assesses the profitability of a bank's assets. The return on assets (ROA) is computed by dividing annual revenue by total assets. The return on equity (ROE) is calculated by dividing net income by shareholders' equity (or divided by net tangible asset

value). Since it represents the bank's profitability on each share, this is the most crucial metric for shareholders. Tobin's Q is the ratio of a tangible asset's market value to its replacement value.

Independent variables include ownership index, dividend pay-out, size of the bank, leverage, liquidity risk, non-performing loans, loan loss provisions. The ownership index includes 11 important indexes to evaluate bank ownership structure. Following [Srairi, 2015](#); [Abdullah & Ismail, 2017](#), this study includes the following ownership structure indexes: 1. disclosure of Institution ownership, 2. Information about share voting and voting agreements, 3. Availability of Investor Relations contact detail, 4. Disclosure of foreign ownership, 5. Nr. of shares held by officers and directors has not decreased by 10% or more 6. Nr. of shares held by officers and directors has increased by 10% or more, 7. Transparency of Capital structure, 8. Government ownership is disclosed 9. Family ownership is disclosed 10. Bank has a policy against insider trading, 11. Elected member of the board. The ownership indexes score is equal to 1 if a bank fulfills the index and otherwise 0. The ownership indexes are calculated by taking the average of all 11 indexes. The operation variables and measurements are shown in the following table;

Table:2

Operation Variables and Measurements

Variable	Notation	Measurement	Reference
Dependent Variables			
ROA	ROA	x100	Trad et al. (2017)
ROE	ROE	x100	Liang et al. (2013)
Tobin's Q	Tobin's Q	$\frac{\text{Equity Market Value} + \text{Debt Book Value}}{\text{Assets Book Value}} \times 100$	Pan and Tian (2014)
Independent Variables			
Bank Ownership Index	BOI	11 score index.	Srairi, 2015; Abdullah & Ismail, 2017
Dividend Pay-out	DVP	$\frac{\text{Dividend Per share}}{\text{Earning Per Share}} * 100$	Zabihi & Ghaleb, 2013
Bank Size	BSIZE	$\ln \text{ Total Assets}$	Foos el al. (2010)
Bank Leverage	BLVG	$\frac{\text{Total Debt}}{\text{Total Assests}} * 100$	Hassan et al., (2016)
Liquidity Risk	LR	$\frac{\text{Net Loans}}{\text{Customer Deposits}} * 100$	Jara-Bertin et al. (2014)

Non-Performing Loans	NPLs	$\frac{NPLs}{Total\ Loans} * 100$	Jones et al. (2013)
Loan Loss Provisions	LLPs	$\frac{LLPs}{Total\ Loans} * 100$	Fu et al. (2014)

3.3 Model Specification

The effect of ownership structure and dividend payout on a bank's financial performance is investigated using the ordinary least squares (OLS) regression approach. The independent variable (explaining variable) is associated with each other and with the dependent variable in this method (variable of interest). [Francesca & Angela, \(2016\)](#); [Predag et al., \(2014\)](#), and [Thierno et al. \(2018\)](#) used the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) approach to investigate the association between ownership structure, dividend payout, and financial performance. The following models have been introduced to investigate the relationship among ownership structure, Dividend pay-out, and financial performance, which are in line with prior literature.

$$ROA_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 BOI_{it} + \beta_2 DVP_{it} + \beta_3 BSIZE_{it} + \beta_4 BLVG_{it} + \beta_5 LR_{it} + \beta_6 NPLS_{it} + \beta_7 LLP_{sit} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots (1)$$

$$ROE_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 BOI_{it} + \beta_2 DVP_{it} + \beta_3 BSIZE_{it} + \beta_4 BLVG_{it} + \beta_5 LR_{it} + \beta_6 NPLS_{it} + \beta_7 LLP_{sit} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots (2)$$

$$Tobin's\ Q_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 BOI_{it} + \beta_2 DVP_{it} + \beta_3 BSIZE_{it} + \beta_4 BLVG_{it} + \beta_5 LR_{it} + \beta_6 NPLS_{it} + \beta_7 LLP_{sit} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots (3)$$

Where,

α = intercept

ε_{it} = error term

β = beta

ROA_{it} = Return on Asset

ROE_{it} = Return on Equity

Tobin's Q_{it} = Market Shareholders' Value Measurement

BOI = Bank Ownership Index

DVP = Dividend Pay-out

BSIZE = Bank Size

BLVG = Bank Leverage

LR = Liquidity Risk

NPLs = Non-Performing Loans

LLPs = Loan Loss Provinces

4. Analysis and Empirical Result

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table:3

Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Dev.
<u>Dependent variable:</u>				
ROA	0.73	2.9	2.1	.423
ROE	0.67	1.7	2.3	.482
Tobin's Q				
<u>Independent Variables</u>				
BOI	16.3	24.56	17.3	7.23
DVP	8.23	14.52	18.4	6.98
BSIZE	4.56	7.23	5.23	4.45
BLVG	7.38	11.34	8.12	3.56
LR	8.45	10.21	13.21	3.56
NPLs	0.01	98.71	7.29	10.98
LLPs	54.97	165.23	1.46	7.74

4.2 Analysis of Correlation

The Pearson correlation matrix was used to identify multicollinearity in explanatory factors, which is compatible with Weisberg (1985). Table 4 shows the correlation matrix of the variables, revealing that the highest simple correlation between the variables was 0.46 between bank size and performance (Tobin's Q). Hair et al. (2006) argue that the association between the independent variables is not an issue until it reaches 0.90. The findings show that the correlation analysis is less than 0.90 which indicates there is no correlation between the variables.

Table: 4

Correlation Matrix between variables

	ROA	ROE	Tobin's Q	BOI	DVP	BSIZE	BLVG	LR	NPLs	LLPs
ROA	1									
ROE	.048***	1								
Tobin's Q	.095***	.035***	1							
BOI	.052***	.019***	.037	1						
DVP	.036**	-.040***	-.0119	.041***	1					
BSIZE	-.018***	.020***	.025***	-.053***	-.020***	1				
BLVG	.039	-.082***	-.012***	.039	.042***	-.065***	1			
LR	.048***	.003	.0001	.063***	.065***	-.017	-.031***	1		
NPLs	-.038***	-.005***	-.018***	.035	.083***	-.020***	.051***	-.011	1	
LLPs	-.031***	-.040***	-.007	.006	.039***	-.001***	.041***	.053**	.062***	1

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

4.3 The Unit Root Test

Table: 5
Unit Root Test

Variable	ADF Test		Philip Person Test	
	Level T-Statistics P- Value	Frist Deference T-Statistics P- Value	Level T-Statistics P- Value	Frist Deference T-Statistics P- Value
ROA	38.0592 0.0087	0.0000 0.0000	48.8975 0.0974	0.0003 0.000
ROE	37.2639 0.0040	0.0000 0.0000	43.3272 0.0013	0.0000 0.0000
Tobin's Q	39.4884 0.0058	0.0000 0.0000	46.3294 0.0007	0.0000 0.0000
BOI	38.0592 0.0087	0.0000 0.0000	48.8975 0.0974	0.0003 0.000
DVP	41.1363 0.0036	0.0000 0.0000	59.1034 0.000	0.000 0.000
BSIZE	0.0000 0.000	43.7792 0.0016	0.000 0.000	59.1665 0.000
BLVG	0.0000 0.0000	51.6696 0.0000	0.0000 0.0000	61.2847 0.0000
LR	38.3432 0.0056	0.0000 0.0000	52.2314 0.000	0.0000 0.0000
NPLs	40.000 0.0000	0.0000 0.0000	39.000 0.0000	0.0000 0.0000
LLPs	0.0000 0.000	43.7792 0.0016	0.000 0.000	59.1665 0.000

4.4 Regression Analysis

The research mainly focuses on the impact of ownership structure and dividend pay-out on the performance of top10 listed banks in GCC countries. The results of regression analysis using OLS for all models are presented in table 6. The findings reveal that there is a positive and significant impact of ownership score indexes on financial performance in all the models (ROA, ROE, Tobin's Q). The result is consistent with the findings of [Srairi, 2015](#); [Abdullah & Ismail, 2017](#). These results supported our premise that banks with a better ownership structure perform better and have a greater market value. It could also indicate that market participants' awareness of the value of strong governance measures has grown over time, leading to greater adoption of those measures by market players and a greater appreciation by shareholders of the influence of those measures on bank performance.

It is evident that the dividend payout and bank's performance have a significant positive relationship, implying that dividend payout should rise in tandem with firm performance (ROA, ROE, Tobin's Q). The findings are compatible with the result of (Zabihi & Ghaleb, 2013). Return on Assets (ROA), which was employed as a proxy for profitability, has a positive and significant impact on company dividend payout, implying that dividend payout should rise in tandem with firm profitability. This research also discovered that the logarithm of total assets, which was employed as a proxy for a bank's size, had a positive significant impact on the performance of banks. It has been demonstrated that the larger banks perform better than those of smaller banks and therefore pay more high dividends.

The study's findings also suggest that leverage played a significant influence in determining the performance of top listed banks in GCC countries as a control variable. The findings show that there is a negative relationship between banks' leverage and the financial performance of banks (ROA, ROE, Tobin's Q). Prior researchers such as (Hassan et al., 2016) conclude the same result. This is likely due to interest payments. When you owe money, you must pay interest to the lender over time. Every dollar you pay in interest deducts the same amount from your profit. The cost of interest may constitute a reasonable investment if you get a low-interest rate on a particular loan. Trade buyers frequently buy inventory on credit and pay interest to cover the cost of the debt. Concerning Liquidity risk (LR), the analysis reveals that it is significant and negatively associated with ROA and positively with ROE and Tobin's Q. The result suggests that a lower loan to total deposit ratio (higher liquidity) increases the profitability of GCC-listed banks. This finding is compatible with the findings of Jara-Bertin et al. (2014) who considered the relationship of banks' loan-to-deposit ratio and ROA is negative. It also suggests a positive correlation between the bank's profitability and its level of liquid assets.

Table: 6
Regression Analysis

Model (1) ROA					Model (2) ROE				
Variables	Coefficient	St. Error	t-statistic	Prob	Variables	Coefficient	St. Error	t-statistic	Prob
BOI	-0.0258	0.01139	-2.26439	0.0269	BOI	-0.02492	0.00926	-2.6901	0.0088
DVP	-0.0027	0.0031	-0.8634	0.0411	DVP	-0.00106	0.0026	-1.1022	0.0339
BSIZE	-0.8272	0.0292	-8.6635	0.0267	BSIZE	-0.00209	0.0012	-1.633	0.0440
BLV	0.0010	0.0625	16.562	0.0382	BLV	0.00106	0.0056	1.8910	0.0267
LR	0.0187	0.0584	13.567	0.0123	LR	0.00344	0.0394	-2.3984	0.1012
NPLs	0.0483	0.0584	-0.437	0.0341	NPLs	0.01948	0.0038	1.8933	0.0289
LLPs	0.0472	0.0289	9.450	0.4984	LLPs	0.0034	0.0384	0.4874	0.0439

Prob(F-statistic)	0	Prob(F-statistic)	0
R ²	0.423	R ²	0.511
Durbin-Watson	1.97	Durbin-Watson	1.58

Model (3) Tobin's Q				
Variables	Coefficient	St. Error	t-statistic	Prob
BOI	-0.0258	0.0113	-2.26439	0.0269
DVP	-0.0027	0.0031	-0.8634	0.0211
Bsize	-0.8235	0.0292	-8.6635	0.0237
BLV	0.0010	0.0625	16.562	0.0392
LR	0.0012	0.0051	12.485	0.0316
NPLs	0.0911	0.0374	0.4734	0.0342
LLPs	0.0384	0.0274	-1.3845	0.1969
Prob(F-statistic)	0			
R ²	0.899763			
Durbin-Watson	1.519708			

As expected, the findings indicate that the relationship between bank performance and the NPL ratio is significantly negative as an indicator of credit risk or asset quality. The greater the NPLs, the smaller the performance of banks. Depositors may need higher interest rates because they think the banks are risky, and therefore, they may obtain lower returns. The findings of the current study support the results of [Jones et al. \(2013\)](#) which suggest poor asset quality (high NPLs) will reduce bank efficiency as much as it limits banks' loanable resource pool. For loan loss provisions, the present study shows that the credit quality calculated by the LLPs ratio has a significantly negative impact on the performance of banks, which supports the findings of [Fu et al. \(2014\)](#) who conclude that banks enhance their profits by reforms that enhance credit quality control and screening. The greater the quality of the LLPs, the lower the bank performance. It is also not shocking; the ratio of LLPs to banks' NPLs in Saudi Arabia, a major nation in the GCC region, grew from 153.3% during the financial crisis to 194% in 2015.

Conclusion

The ownership structure literature focuses on the type of ownership and does not pay sufficient attention to the importance of the ownership structure index. Motivated by recent development in

integrating an institutional perspective with a traditional agency perspective in ownership structure studies (see eg., [Nguyen et al., 2015](#); [Almudehki and Zeitun, 2013](#); [Srairi, 2015](#)), this study attempts to document the impact of ownership structure index and dividend payout on the financial performance of 10 top listed banks in GCC countries by applying ordinary least square (OLS) approach on the dataset. The study includes NPLs, LLPs, market risk, liquidity, and bank leverage to control for bank risk-taking and its size. The study comprises of the top listed banks in GCC countries covering the period 2009-2020 (post-crisis). The findings reveal that bank ownership as measured by score indexes has a positive and significant impact on the financial performance of listed banks in GCC countries. It also emphasizes that ownership structure is a significant determinant of bank performance. The study concludes that there is a positive association between a bank's profitability and dividends payout which suggests that large banks pay more dividends. The analysis shows that bank risk as measured by NPLs and LLPs has negatively affected bank profitability. It also reveals that leverage and a bank's performance have a negative relationship since the bank needs to pay interest on debt and that ultimately leads to profit deduction.

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